

INSECURITY AND STATE COLLAPSE: LESSONS FOR NIGERIA IN THE TWENTY FIRST CENTURY

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Abstract

This paper examines the state of Nigerian nation from security perspective. It notes that evidences of state collapse are already in fuller operation in Nigeria. It further notes that whether Nigeria stands or fails it has far-reaching implications for the world and Africa. Among factors pushing the nation to the precipice identified in the paper are unemployment, violent ethno-religious conflict, terrorism, policy failure, among others. Gleaning from evidence on the collapse of the Holy Roman Empire, the disintegration and decay of pre-colonial empires and kingdoms in West Africa, the bitter experience of the Nigerian Civil War, the balkanisation of India and Pakistan, the collapse of USSR and the emergence of several Slavic States, civil unrests and the political divorce of South Sudan in 2011, the paper argues that hope is not lost if Nigeria takes the lessons of history seriously and sees the danger of insecurity troubling her and the need arrest it.

Introduction

The international system of the twenty-first century will be marked by a seeming contradiction: on the one hand, fragmentation; on the other, growing globalization.¹

Some would have doubted the fulfillments of this brilliant prediction made by Henry Alfred Kissinger in 1994 following the epic liquidation of the Union of the Soviet Socialist Republic (USSR), but the resurgence of terrorism and violent ethno-religious conflicts with its heavy burden on states across the

¹ C.W. Kegley *etal*, *World Trend and Transformation*.,New York :St. Martin's Press (N.d), 546. G O. Odeh, "Globalization and

African Development: Where Are We and Where Are We Going in the Twenty-First Century" in *Journal of Globalization and International Studies*, O O.Okpeh Jr,(ed), (6) 1 &2, 2012,92.

globe have helped accelerated and accentuated the fulfillments of the thesis. The fall of one of the European giants, the USSR in 1991 remained one of the momentous events in State collapse discourse in contemporary world politics. Since then, the possibilities of state collapse or state failure is no longer a myth, but reality. Currently, African states are over burdened with socio-economic, political and cultural stress, which they find difficult to navigate through in the century. This paper is an attempt to explore some of the fundamental characteristics of state collapse which are seriously manifesting in Nigeria and making many doubt if the country is not failing or failed already. The paper is structured into the following; introduction, manifestations/ characteristics of state collapse, lessons for Nigeria and finally, the conclusion.

Concept of insecurity

Insecurity is derived from the word security. "Security" is derived from the old French and Latin *securite* and *securus*, which denotes "free" and "care" respectively.² This freedom and care applies to nations and citizens. The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), cited in Atagher, tied security to law and order, protection of lives, properties and the corporate existence of

² A. A. Williams, W. T. Adetayo s and O. T. Abigail, "Poetry as Tool for Promoting National Integration and Security: A Case Study of the Poem of Oladele Sangotoye "Etutu Isokan" in S. I. Odinye (ed.), *Interdisciplinary Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 1 (2), 2016,106.

the Nigerian State.³ This pitched the concept in the tent of national security, which Aji, partly puts as preservation of our independence and sovereignty, safety and freedom from anxiety or danger in such a manner that one's future can be certain and guaranteed.⁴ Some commentators put the phenomenon as "freedom from danger, risk or loss".⁵ The concept of national security is held to have been introduced after the World War II,⁶ but its practice dates to the Treaty of Westphalia (Peace of Westphalia) 1646-1648.⁷ Thomas Hobbes cited in Helga, argues that, citizens submits to a powerful sovereign who promises an end to civil and religious war, and bringing forth a lasting

³ I. Atagher, "Democracy and Instability in Nigeria: Implications for National Security, Integration and Unity" in FASS (BSU) Journal of Faculty Arts Seminar Series, (2) 2004, 20.

⁴ B. G. Aji, "Youth and National Development" in *Constructive Engagement on National Security on the theme: Youth Empowerment and National Security: Options for Nigeria*,(1),6. G.O. Olankeju (eds). Journal Publication of Alumni Association of National Defence College (AANDEC/NDC), Abuja: National Defence College, 2014, XIX.

⁵ NYSC, Security Awareness and Education Handbook for NYSC Corps Members and Staff, 4th Edition, 2016, 12.

⁶ N.A. Agbo, "Emergence of Terrorism: A Challenge to Nigerian National Security and Economic Development- An Overview of bomb blasts on Independence Day; Jos and Mogadishu Barracks" in *Soja, A Magazine of Nigerian Army*, 2nd Edition, 3rd & 4th Quarters. Singapore: Suncraft: 2011, 79.

⁷ H.J. Morgenthau, *Politics Among Nations: The Struggle for Power and Peace*. Sixth Edition, New Delhi: Kalyani Publishers, 2012, 294.

peace and giving him right to conducting policy, including waging war or negotiating for peace for the good of the "Commonwealth."⁸ This is the root of national security mandate. As a matter of fact, continuous fear of sudden death resulting from attacks due to the narcissistic nature of man erected the platform for peace negotiation and the construction of national security body. The Clausewitz ideas of diplomacy and war as instruments of pursuing national cause gave another serious boost to the idea of national security sought by nations exercising self-interest.⁹

Though the term (national security) came into usage in US political discourse in 1943,¹⁰ it was first mentioned in 1790 at

⁸ H. Helga, "The Security Puzzle: Theory-Building and Discipline Building in International Security" in *International Studies Quarterly*, Blackwell Publishers, (n.d), 35(1)3-17 doi.co.2307/2600386, Jstor 2600386. See also, G.O.Odeh, "Historicising National Elections and Their Implications on National Security and Integration in Contemporary Nigerian State: Centenary Discourse" in *International Journal of Arts and Sciences (IJAS)*, Vol. No.4, J.Azzopardi and J. Bonnici (eds). At: <http://www.universitypublications.net/ijas/0804/index.html2015>.

⁹ J.C. Johari, *International Relations and Politics: Theoretical Perspectives in the Post Cold War Era.*, 466-467.

¹⁰ J.K. Bartolotto, *The Origin and Developmental Process of the National Security Strategy*. USAWC Strategy Research Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements of the Master of Strategic Studies Degree, U.S. Army War College, Carlisle Barracks, Pennsylvania, 17013, at: www.dtic.mil/cgi-bin/getTRDOC?ADA423358.

the Yale University in relations to domestic industries.¹¹ Understandingly, at 1945 and thereafter, most of the significant threats to state security were internal, rather than external. This development affected the narrative of peace and international relations. Whatever the case, the security of a state may be threatened by developments that threatens the monopoly of violence either through external invasion or global rebellion. National security has been offered multiple definitions by scholars, but few would be taken. To Hans Morgenthau, cited in Agbo, national security connotes:

The integrity of the national territory and its institutions, national defence and security, protection of a country from attack or subversion, preparedness for military action, diligence in matters of intelligence gathering and secrecy, and protection of resources and rights considered critical to the functioning of a nation are all included in

¹¹ G.O.Odeh, "Historicising National Elections and Their Implications on National Security and Integration in Contemporary Nigerian State: Centenary Discourse" in *International Journal of Arts and Sciences (IJAS)*, Vol. No.4, J.Azzopardi and J. Bonnici (eds). At: <http://www.universitypublications.net/ijas/0804/index.html2015>.

national defence and security plans.¹²

The above realist's conception is state-centric and limited in scope considering the current security threats confronting nations. Paleri, cited in Odeh, puts the concept as:

The measurable states of the capability of a nation to overcome the multi-dimensional threats to the apparent wellbeing of its people and its survival as a nation state at any given time, by balancing all instruments of policy through governance can be indeed by computation, empirically or otherwise and is extendable to global security by variables external to it.¹³

The above blends economic, social, political and other forms of security threats to nations. The changing focus of security led to the rethinking of security framework that consummated in the securitization of human needs i.e tying security to development that became prominent in the post Soviet era.

Be that as it may, the emphasis here is not so much concern with security-development interfacial argument, but exploration of several issues that enhances understanding of security

¹² N.A. Agbo, "Emergence of Terrorism: A Challenge to Nigerian National Security and Economic Development...", 79.

¹³ G.O.Odeh, "Historicising National Elections and Their..."

threats in Nigeria, which include: economic security, food security, health security, environmental security, personal security, community security and political security that are fallouts of the cold war politics, internalized or domesticated by the vulnerability of Nigerian state. It is on record that the refusal of UK and US to supply military aircrafts and weapons during the civil war made the Federal Government of Nigeria turned to the Soviet Union for help.¹⁴ Ecologically, Britain is the originator of environmental pollution. Toyo substantiates this asserting that Britain remains the originator as the first industrial capitalist power *alias* the "workshop of the world".¹⁵ This was to translate into new security threats that have continued to attract the attention of Nigerian government and the international community.

An Ideal State, which is utopia, is a state of absence of espionage, sabotage, subversion, hijack and violent destruction of lives and properties. The activities of insurgent groups, herdsmen, militants, economic woes among others, constitute insecurity. Security has to be more about steps taken to prevent rather than treating espionage or spying and

¹⁴ C. Achebe, *There Was A Country: A Personal History of Biafra*. London: Penguin Books, P. 104. A Adenije, "Ideology, Cold War Politics and Eastern European Economic Assistance to Nigeria, 1960-1979"...,34.

¹⁵ E. Toyo, *Background to Globalization*, Academic Publication Series 2. Ibadan: ASUU, 2000, 15.

all forms of attacks (passive and violent) theft etc.,. Given that an ideal state is utopia, the concern of security experts should be to assess threats, vulnerability and evaluate the risk in order to eliminate possible damages or losses.

Manifestations of State Collapse

As socio-economic and political malady, state collapse/failure essentially refers to the situation in which the basic functions of state are no longer performed. Where functions are performed as ritual or mere ceremony and no meaningful headway is made indicates the state is comatose and a ghost of itself. As a condition or status of affairs of a State, there are certain symptoms and features that are observable before a State can be designated as buckled or failed. Zartman, contends that a State may be said to be failing or designated collapse when the following distress conditions strongly manifests:

As the decision making centre of government, the State is paralyzed and inoperative: Laws are not made, order is not preserved, and societal cohesion is not enhanced. As a symbol of identity, it has lost its power of conferring a name on its people and a meaning to their social action. As a territory, it is no longer assured security and provisionment by a central sovereign organization. As the authoritative political institution, it has lost its legitimacy, which

is therefore up for grabs, and so has lost its right to command and conduct public affairs. As a system of socio-economic organization, its functional balance of inputs and output is destroyed, it no longer receives support from nor exercises control over its people, and it is no longer even the target of demands, because its people know that it is incapable of providing supplies.¹⁶

The above shows feature that make up State collapse. Deep introspection made analysts to wonder if most African States including Nigeria have not collapsed. The question asked sometimes is whether the condition of African States is not worse than they were under colonial times. Because of advances in knowledge vocabulary or using more pleasant euphemism synonyms such as recession, depression, downturn, slump, economy in a bad shape have been developed to coat the true picture of affairs in Nigeria and other African states. These synonyms or euphemism means collapse in the true sense of their meanings. Mazrui, cited in Yandaki, is more blunt and incisive, putting it that:

Contemporary Africa is in the throes of decay and

¹⁶ I.W. Zartman, "Introduction: Posing the Problem of State Collapse" *Collapsed States: The Disintegration and Restoration of Legitimate Authority*, I.M. Zartman, London: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1995, 5.

decomposition. Even the degree of dependent modernization achieved under colonial rule is being reversed. Successive collapse of State in African country one after another during the 1990s suggests a once unthinkable solution: recolonization. To an increasing number of Africans, this is the bitter message that has emerged from the horrifying events in Rwanda. While Africans have been quite successful in uniting to achieve national freedom, we have utterly failed to unite for economic development and political stability. War, famine and ruin is the postcolonial legacy for too many Africans.¹⁷

Put differently Yandaki asks thus:

Can a state being threatened with disintegration like Zaire or Nigeria act as the basis for regional cooperation or unity? As for peace-keeping role, to what degree has Nigeria succeeded in bringing about stability in Liberia? Like with Mobutu Sese Seko's Zaire. How can a force of a country which behaves like an army of occupation to its own people keep regional peace?...Also with

¹⁷ A I.Yandaki, *The State in Africa: A Critical Study in Historiography and Political Philosophy*, Zaria: Gaskiya Corporation Ltd, 2015, 197.

(post- apartheid) South Africa, with its predominantly white army. Here is an army which only until the dawn of this decade was harassing all the frontline states, killing its people, destabilizing the political economy and so on. Will it be acceptable to its erstwhile victims?¹⁸

If for leniency, Nigeria and most African States have not failed, the general insecurity situation is fast tracking their total collapse. Among the glaring challenges confronting Nigeria and most African States in the century is the inability to meet the basic needs and demands of the plurality of the people. The feeling of despair, frustration which often leads to aggression and deprivation gives impetus to violent extremism, crime and insecurity that is capable of finally liquidating Nigerian State, as most African States.

More than fifty eight years after independence and several political engagements at reforms, Nigeria is neither going forward nor backward. The manifestation, deterioration and perpetuation of the following marks Nigeria as being on the fast lane to failure or shadow state: One, beyond the sign, there is an economic failure. This made the International Monetary Fund (IMF) advisors, Xavier Sala Martin and Arvin Subramanian to have described

¹⁸ A I. Yandaki, *The State in Africa:....*, 198. G O.Odeh,

Nigeria as a “metaphor per excellence for a failed development experience”. And in the same tone, Ambassador Princeton Layman asked whether Nigeria is not losing it in terms of economic (industrial) influence, strategic importance and global relevance in the twenty first century.¹⁹ The country for sure has failed compared to countries it started the journey with, and which she was even ahead of particularly Asian countries that are now power to reckon with in international politics. Agriculture, knocked out by oil minerals has failed and several attempts at reviving it through diversification of economy by successive governments have not yielded the expected fruits. The bulk of the challenges Nigeria political economy has faced for years and is still facing originated from oil. From 1973 to 2001 or so, the “natural resource curse” aspect of oil was dominant, leading to stagnation and embarrassing decline in the quality of lives of Nigeria as measured by Human Development Index. Between 1970 and 2001, Nigeria received \$ 300 billion and in spite of this, the nation’s per capita income dropped from \$264 to 256²⁰ and since then, the

¹⁹ R. Babalola, *The Paradox of a Nation: A Socio-Economic Perspective*, Being a lecture delivered at the 2nd Annual Olashore Lecture at the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, 15th February ,2010,2-3. See also, G O.Odeh. *The 1914 Amalgamation of Nigeria as a Precursor to Integration at a Crossroads: One Hundred Years After*. Makurdi: Gwatex Publishers, 2015.

²⁰ N . Okonjo- Iweala, “Securing a Diversified Economic Future for Nigeria” in *Nigeria: Half a*

condition has not changed. In 2013, Human Development Index (HDI) report revealed that Nigeria was lagging behind all West African countries, except Sierra Leone.²¹ Nigeria failed to invest in education, health and nutrition. There is daily increase in delinquency. The country infant mortality rate as at 2018 is that 102 out of 1000 children, that is 1 out of 5 Nigeria children died before the age of five and the country occupied the 11th position as one of the most unsafe countries in the world to give birth in as at 2018.²² The political and resource control agitation that have claimed a lot of lives revolves round the curse angle of the oil, the so called national cake to be grabbed and shared by ethnic and tribal political jingoists. The nation lacked effective industrial base for economic take off, no petrochemical industry to fuel the industrialization process, no effective iron and steel complex to produce flat steel as Ajaoukuta Mill up to 2018 remain comatose dispute political promises.

Two, the neo-colonial trapping of the country spells doom for the nation. Over the decades Nigeria has continued to implement policies and programmes of the Bretton Wood Institutions (IBRD and

Century of Progress and Challenges, C C. Ikokwu (ed), Nigeria: True Expression Press, 2011, 59.

²¹ S. Momah, *Nigeria Beyond Divorce: Amalgamation in Perspective*, Ibadan: Safari Books, Ltd, 2013,176.

²² *WHO/ Nigeria*, <http://www.who.int/snigeria/index>.

IMF). The frequent pilgrimage of government officials to headquarters of western imperialism, and acquiring of houses over there, rushing to hospitals and medical vacation in foreign lands, while facilities at home are left unattended to thereby necessitating ASUU strikes, all these showcase a country that is at the edge of collapse. Vladimir Putin may have captured the state of African States, thus:

When the African becomes rich, his bank accounts are in Switzerland. He travels to France for medical treatment. He invests in Germany. He buys from Dubai. He consumes Chinese. He prays in Rome or Mecca. His children study in Europe. He travels to Canada, USA, and Europe for tourism. If he dies, he will be buried in his native country Africa. Africa is just a cemetery for Africans. How can a cemetery developed?²³

The above raises several issues. First the height of riches Europe and America have attained today has its history in the looting, plundering and raping of Africa in the eras of the trans Atlantic slave trade, colonialism and neocolonialism. The evils of those eras defined the state of Africa today. If America and Europe had been looted and plundered like

²³ “Russian President Vladimir Putin Says Africa is a Cemetery for Africans”, at <https://cnyakundi.com>.

Africa it wouldn't have been where it is today. If Africa is a grave yard, America and Europe convert it. After all, it is not only Africans that have been buried in Africa even the whites too particularly the European anthropologists, explorers and others. L S B Leakey, cited in Adejo, dismisses such old European propaganda that:

Critics of Africa forget that men of science today are, with few exceptions, satisfied that Africa was the birth place of man himself, and that for many centuries thereafter Africa was in the forefront of all world progress.²⁴

Adding to the above, development in settled life proved decisive in human historical progress and it was clear that Africa was ahead of others in this sedentary life. When some European nations were still hunters and gatherers using stones of Mesolithic or Middle Stone Age culture, Africans had conveniently abandoned that for some three to six hundred years earlier. African leaders and business men's habits of hoarding money overseas, building of houses over there and medical vacation are some of the fundamental psychological fallouts of the European carnal knowledge of Africa. Putin, may be one of the racial jingoists, but frankly; Africa may not need to rely

²⁴ A M. Adejo, *Reparations: Africa's New Charge in Changing World*, Makurdi: Peach Global Publications, 2004, 10.

on such old achievements and absolved herself and the leadership of the blame. The question is, for how long are we going to blame America and Europe for the crime of the periods? Countries that experienced slavery and colonialism are on their feet since the last quarter of the twentieth century. Nigeria's position in corruption perception index released by Transparency International despite the claimed efforts of the President Muhammadu Buhari to fighting it shows that the country is a formidable force in the so called Africa cemetery. The crisis of development arises from the character of African leaders and the economically well-to-do that throw the helpless masses into security threats.

By the way of manifestations of collapsing and failing state together, it is noted that, Nigeria:

(a) Emerged 3rd position in 2018 global terrorism ranking coming behind Iraq and Afghanistan in World Terrorism Index. This is despite the heavy government expenditure on military hardware and international supports.²⁵ The inability of the military to combat and crush terrorism particularly Boko Haram has left many wondering! If it took the Nigerian Military with crude weapon thirty months to win the Civil War and hours and days to crush several skirmishes in the country, even across its border since the colonial time, how long should it

take the Nigerian military to crush Boko Haram?

- (b) Has remained an extractive and primary economy that produces unrefined raw materials for export, either in form of agricultural products or crude oil. Manufacturing is at a very rudimentary stage and industrialization remained an inconsequential factor in the nation's economic template. This accounts for high rate of poverty and unemployment leading to back way migration of the youths to Europe and America.
- (c) Has continued as a nation that has failed to invest in research and education, in which the total number of students studying in various universities in Ghana alone during the late Musa Yar'dua/ Dr. Goodluck Ebele Jonathan administration paid not less than 155 billion naira as tuition annually compared to the Federal Government annual budget of 121 billion naira for university education.²⁶ This trend has not changed even under Muhammadu Buhari/Yemi Osibanjo administration. The Tertiary

²⁵ Daily Sun, Friday, December 2, 2018.

²⁶ G O.Odeh, "An Ideological Framework for Effective Resource Acquisition and Management: A Comparative Analysis of Nigeria and Selected Asian Countries, 1960-2014" in *VUNA Journal of History and International Relations*, (2),2 ,T Ayemga (ed), A Biannual Publication of the Department of History and International Relations, VERITAS University (The Catholic University of Nigeria), Abuja-Nigeria, 323.

- Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and educational stake holders too are not helping matter in this regard as they encouraged overseas studies than local studies.
- (d) Remained a country where none of its university has made it up to the list of 500 top universities in global ranking due to institutional decay and neglect.
- (e) Has being a huge market for cell phones with a population of well over 150 million people using GSM and yet, no single cell phone is produced in the country despite the government professed and preferred support to Science and Engineering above humanities. Along this line, Engineer John Enoh, an Idoma graduate of Computer Science from Benue State University, Makurdi and a staff of Sonny Ericson, residing in the United States of America uplifted Nigeria from backwaters of the GSM world on 1st December, 2018 by the launch of Beep tool, the cheapest android cell phone ever in the globe named Oyi-1 (an Idoma name for son, guy or man). However, Nigeria still have a long way to go along this endeavour.
- (f) Is a country which over the years fails to understand the rudiments of technology transfer that owners of technologies do not willingly transfer techniques, but those interested do so cleverly as was the case with Asian countries.
- (g) Is a country which in ten years spent over 300 billion naira on technology transfer agreement, which failed woefully as medicines in our hospitals, are imported, gadgets in the banks are imported; machineries used in companies are imported; and satellites NIGCOMSAT 1 and NIGCOMSAT 1R are imported.
- (h) Remained a country where every action of government has religious and ethnic interpretation showing the inherent differences among the people and near absolute dearth of patriotism.
- (i) Perpetually remained a country where the law court find it very difficult to convict criminals and where no high and mighty sponsor or perpetrators of organized and violent crime have ever been brought to book;
- (j) Have continued as a country where in broad day light, thugs stormed the National Assembly, the highest legislative chamber (Senate Chamber) of the country and made away with the Maze disrupting the session proceedings and no one heard the security report of the incidence again due to political interest.
- (k) Is a country where youths and adult find it easy to procure tramadol and others hard drugs than paracetamol for headache.
- (l) Have remained a country where unauthorized person carries dangerous weapon around the streets

and takes same to political party rallies in the name of political thugs and if he kills, he goes free; and
(m) Remained a country that has for decades ignored the fundamentals of Public Security and whose average rate of crime detection continued to stagger at one percent (1%). Thus, children, youths and adults virtually disappear almost every day even in the hands of security personnel.²⁷

Added to the above is the report that between January and May 2017, no fewer than 10,000 Nigerians died while illegally migrating to Europe through the Mediterranean Sea and deserts to escape unemployment and poverty (if you like state collapse). Out of the figure, 4,900 persons were established to have died on the sea in the process, while the rest died in the desert.²⁸ In November 2017, International Organisation for Migration (IOM), cited in Adejokun, revealed that Nigerians were sold at the rate of \$400 per head in Libya. While the male works in the farms and mines, the females were

²⁷ M H. Nyako, “ Issues in Report on the Restoration of Special Security Committee of PDP Governors’ Forum Dated 23rd,2013” in G O.Odeh (ed) *Interrogating the PDP and the Rise of APC: Issues in the Selected Speeches of Murtala Hamman-Yero Nyako*, Makurdi: Gwatex publishers, 2018, 45. G O.Odeh, "An Ideological Framework for Effective Resource Acquisition and Management..."³²³. Others who commented on the argument raised in the section pledged anonymous.

²⁸ S Adejokun, *Unemployment rise as NBS prepares new data*, <https://www.tribuneonline.com>.

used as sex toys and labourers.²⁹ Significant numbers of Nigeria’s professionals in various fields of human endeavor are in Europe, the Americas and Asia as world bests because of our inclement system. The above, among others are manifestations of a weakening and failing state, which create fertile ground for all kind of insecurity to thrive.

Lessons for Nigeria

Issues of state collapse are not new in history. In 476 AD the famous Roman Empire crumbled and its territories were inhabited by barbaric hordes.³⁰ Consequently, Europe went into a period of darkness defined in her history as middle Ages that lasted from 476 AD to 1492, when America was discovered. About the second half of the 11th century, when William Normandy invaded England, Ghana Empire founded in the 8th century was the most powerful kingdom in West Africa. It suffered disintegration in the late 11th century and was replaced by Sosso Empire, which collapsed in 1240 following the battle of Karina. By 1346, the year of the battle of Crecy, Mali was in existence and by 15th century when the City State of Gao made bid for independence the empire went into regional power oblivion under

²⁹ S Adejokun, *Unemployment rise as NBS prepares new data*,...

³⁰ B V. Rao, *World History*, New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 2003, 158. D O. Ajao, *Outline History of the Ancient World from Creation to the Decline of Rome*, Ibadan: Peju International, 1952,87-88.

Sundiata. Consequently, the power vacuum it created was filled in the same 15th century by Songhai Empire of Sunni Ali, which was liquidated in 1591 as a result of the Moroccan invasion.³¹ There were smaller states that has also gone into extinction such as Bambara kingdom, Manlike kingdom, the kemedougou kingdom, the Ashanti, Dahomey, the shrinking of territorial expansion of Sokoto Caliphate in the 19th century, Nri, Ife, Benin (Bini), Oyo, Kanem Borno, Kwarararfa confederacy, among others. As powerful as they were, they are no more. In memories of these kingdoms and empires their peoples and governments named streets and other projects after them in contemporary time. In Asia for instance, India and Pakistan were divided in 1947 signaling the demise of the larger political entity that hosted the two together.³² Between 1992 and 1993, the map of European political geography was redrawn arising from states fragmentation. For instance:

- a. The Union of Soviet Socialist Republic disintegrated into a loosely tied common wealth of independent states whose members threaten to splinter through ethno-national conflict into still more, smaller independent state.

³¹ A M.Adejo, *Reparations: Africa's New Charge in Changing World*, 13. A. Odoemene, "Warfare and Diplomacy in Precolonial West Africa" in *Perspectives in African History*, C B N.Ogbogbo (ed),2011,24-25.

³² B V. Rao, *World History*, 346-347.

- b. Czechoslovakia was formally reconstituted the Czech and Slovak Federal Republics.
- c. Civil war in Yugoslavia ripped the former United Slavic Federation into six independent states, and four proceeded to wage war against each other for control of territory;
- d. Ethnic conflict in Romania, Bulgaria, Macedonia and elsewhere threatened to fragment these warring nationalities into new European States.³³

Back here in contemporary Africa, after decades of civil unrest and loss of about two million people, South Sudan seceded from Sudan and became the newest world nation state since July 2011.³⁴ Nigeria's corporate existence was seriously tested from 1967 to 1970 during the Civil War. Since the War, Nigeria has been in a state of suppressed, "silent", "structural" or "repressive" violence punctuated by periodic outbreaks of actual violence, some causing significant casualties and making thousands refugees in their own country.³⁵ The circumstances that led to

³³ C W. Kegley *etal*, *World Tend and Transformation*, 545. O.O. Okpeh Jr., *The Collapse of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republic and its Implications for the World Order*, Unpublished paper, 1992,5-7.

³⁴ *Two Sudans: The Separation of Africa's Largest Country and Road Ahead*, <https://2012-2017usaid.gov>frontlines>.

³⁵ O. Ibeanu & R. Luckham, *Niger- Delta: Political Violence, Governance and Corporate*

the Nigerian Civil War have not changed. The level of ethno-religious and regional differences in Nigeria at the moment is alarming and unprecedented in her history. Nigeria should be warned that socio-economic, political, cultural and religious factor touching internal wrangling and squabble over leadership succession, profligacy of the leaders, welfare of the people, ethnic, sectional, religious interest and external pressure disrupted the balance of power of states recorded as collapsed in history. Though history hardly repeats itself as the professional school would have us believe the greatest lesson it teaches is that people refuses to learn from the lessons of history.

Conclusion

Analysis of this paper points that evidence of state collapse manifests already in Nigeria. However, all hope is not lost if the country takes the lessons of history seriously. The incontrovertible facts about the position of Nigeria in Africa remains whether it falls or stands for any of this has far-reaching implications for the world and Africa in particular. In falling or standing, this study identifies unemployment, violent ethno-religious conflict, and terrorism and how they are managed to be very vital to the success or failure of the Nigerian project. After surviving a traumatic fratricidal civil war (1967-1970), which lasted for over three years,

events since the return to civil rule in 1999 has continued to showcase the failure of the post civil war reconstruction project. The collapse of the Roman Empire, the disintegration and decay of pre-colonial empires and kingdoms in West Africa, the bitter experience of the Nigerian Civil War, the collapse of USSR and the emergence of several Slavic States and their civil unrest as well as the political divorce of South Sudan in 2011 should teach Nigeria lessons on the danger of insecurity and the need to address it.

Responsibility in a Petro- State, Abuja: Centre for Democracy and Development,2006, 2-3.

